

**ABSOLUTE GRAVITY MEASUREMENTS AT THE ALPINE
RESEARCH CENTRE IN OBERGUGL (AUSTRIA)
IN SEPTEMBER 2018**

Final Report

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Foreword

This report contains the results of absolute gravity measurements carried out at Alpine Research Centre (University of Innsbruck) in Obergurgl. The measurements took place on the pier 0-173-02 (Figure 1) in September 2018.

The absolute gravimeter FG5X#216 was operated by Olivier Francis and Sajad Tabibi from the University of Luxembourg.

The measurements are part of an on-going research collaboration between the Geophysics Laboratory of the University of Luxembourg and Christian Ullrich from the Bundesamt für Eich- und Vermessungswesen (BEV, Federal Office of Metrology and Surveying) in Vienna, Austria.

After the completion of the measurements, the pier was occupied with the FG5#242 of the BEV. The comparison of the g -values will be used to estimate the offset between both gravimeters to ensure consistency of the results while different gravimeters will be used in the coming years.

Figure 1. Pier at the Alpine Research Centre (University of Innsbruck) in Obergurgl.

Data processing

Raw data from the absolute gravimeters consist of vectors of time and position of the falling object during the drops. To obtain the gravity value, a linear equation representing the equation of motion is fit to the raw data including the gravity gradient which has been measured with relative meters.

The data processing follows the protocol adopted during absolute gravimeters comparisons at the BIPM in Sèvres (Francis and van Dam, 2003). Geophysical corrections are applied to the raw gravity data: Earth tides using modelled tidal parameters, atmospheric pressure effect using a constant admittance, and the polar motion effect using pole positions from the International Earth Rotation Service (<http://hpiers.obspm.fr>).

The g-soft v9.12.04.23 software from Microg-LaCoste Inc. was used for the processing. All the text outputs as well as some figures are compiled in the annexes of this report for future reference.

Vertical Gravity Gradient

The vertical gravity gradient is needed to linearize the equation of motion but also to transfer the measured absolute gravity value from the reference height around 1.3 m to the desired height (1.22 in the present report). Its determination requires relative measurements using a smaller and portable relative gravimeter. We used $-1.82 \mu\text{Gal}/\text{cm}$. This value was provided by Christian Ullrich.

Results of the absolute gravity measurements

The FG5X#216 operated from the 17th of September 2018 at 09:45 UTC until the 8th of September 2018 at 12:55 UTC. A total of 51 sets of 100 drops (1 drop /10 sec) were taken with a rate of 1 set per hour. It represents a total of 5100 drops.

Site	Gravity value/ μGal	Mean Set Standard Deviation/ μGal
AGM @ 1.22 m	980 239 670.04	0.66

Reference

Francis O., van Dam T.M., Processing of the Absolute data of the ICAG01, Cahiers du Centre Européen de Géodynamique et de Séismologie, vol.22, 45-48, 2003.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7890604>

ANNEXES

STATION: Alpine Research Centre (University of Innsbruck) in Obergurgl			
City:	Obergurgl	Country:	Austria
Location:	Alpine Research Centre	Particularity:	
Situation:	Pier 0-173-02	Remarks:	
Date:	17-18 September 2018		
Code number:	0-173-02		
Latitude:	46.86709 degrees		
Longitude:	11.02489 degrees		
Elevation:	1935.40 m		
Gradient:	-1.82 $\mu\text{gal/cm}$		
Reference height	0.1290 m + 1.2583 m = 1.3873 m		
Meter:	FG5X		
S/N:	216		
Tidal corrections using observed tidal parameters			
Polar motion correction		Air pressure correction	
X-coordinate	0.2121 Arc seconds	Nominal air pressure:	801.35 mbar
Y-coordinate	0.3502 Arc seconds	Barometric admittance factor	0.3 $\mu\text{gal/mbar}$
Gravity			
Set gravity mean:	980 239 670.04	microgal	
Set std. dev.:	0.66	microgal	
Mean std. dev.:	6.13	microgal	
Number of sets:	51		
Number of drops per set:	100		
Drop interval:	10 seconds		
Set interval:	60 minutes		
Nominal/datum height:	1.22 m		
Author: O. Francis		University of Luxembourg	
Date: October 10, 2018			

Project file

Micro-g LaCoste g Processing Report
File Created: 11/06/18, 12:47:56

Project Name: OB201809
g Acquisition Version: 9.160516
g Processing Version: 9.120423

Company/Institution:
Operator: Olivier Francis

Station Data

Name: OBERGURLP
Site Code: PIER 0-173-02
Lat: 46.86709 Long: 11.02489 Elev: 1935.40 m
Setup Height: 12.90 cm
Transfer Height: 122.00 cm
Actual Height: 138.73 cm
Gradient: -1.820 μ Gal/cm
Nominal Air Pressure: 801.35 mBar
Barometric Admittance Factor: 0.30
Polar Motion Coord: 0.2121 " 0.3502 "
Earth Tide (ETGTAB) Selected
Potential Filename: C:\gData\gWavefiles\ETCPOT.dat
Delta Factor Filename: D:\ABSOLU\DATA\INI\OceanLoad-OBERGURLP.dff

Delta Factors

Start	Stop	Amplitude	Phase	Term
0.000000	0.000001	1.000000	0.0000	DC
0.000002	0.249951	1.160000	0.0000	Long
0.721500	0.906315	1.154250	0.0000	Q1
0.921941	0.974188	1.154240	0.0000	O1
0.989049	0.998028	1.149150	0.0000	P1
0.999853	1.216397	1.134890	0.0000	K1
1.719381	1.906462	1.161720	0.0000	N2
1.923766	1.976926	1.161720	0.0000	M2
1.991787	2.002885	1.161720	0.0000	S2
2.003032	2.182843	1.161720	0.0000	K2
2.753244	3.081254	1.07338	0.0000	M3
3.791964	3.937897	1.03900	0.0000	M4

Ocean Load ON, Filename: D:\ABSOLU\DATA\INI\OceanLoad-OBERGURLP.olf

Waves: M2 S2 K1 O1 N2 P1 K2 Q1 Mf Mm Ssa
Amplitude (μ Gal): 1.447 0.478 0.134 0.135 0.294 0.047 0.125 0.037 0.000 0.000 0.000
Phase (deg): 56.2 28.4 71.9 -188.8 73.5 84.3 26.6 -131.8 0.0 0.0 0.0

Instrument Data

Meter Type: FG5
Meter S/N: X216
Factory Height: 125.83 cm
Rubidium Frequency: 10000000.00000 Hz
Laser: WEO100 (242)
ID: 632.99117754 nm (0.25 V)
IE: 632.99119473 nm (-0.25 V)
IF: 632.99121259 nm (-0.65 V)
IG: 632.99123023 nm (-1.03 V)
IH: 632.99136890 nm (-1.63 V)
II: 632.99139822 nm (-1.38 V)
IJ: 632.99142704 nm (-1.15 V)
Modulation Frequency: 8333.340 Hz

Processing Results

Date: 09/18/18
Time: 00:15:42
DOY: 261
Year: 2018
Time Offset (D h:m:s): 0 0:0:0
Gravity: 980239670.04 μ Gal
Set Scatter: 0.66 μ Gal
Measurement Precision: 0.09 μ Gal
Total Uncertainty: 0.09 μ Gal
Number of Sets Collected: 53
Number of Sets Processed: 51
Set #s Processed:
2,3,4,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20,21,22,23,24,25,26,27,28,29,30,31,32,33,34,35,36,37,38,39,40,41,
42,43,44,45,46,47,48,49,50,51,52,53
Number of Sets NOT Processed: 2
Set #s NOT Processed: 1,5
Number of Drops/Set: 100
Total Drops Accepted: 5074
Total Drops Rejected: 26
Total Fringes Acquired: 1100
Fringe Start: 2
Processed Fringes: 1030
GuideCard Multiplex: 4
GuideCard Scale Factor: 250

Acquisition Settings
Set Interval: 60 min
Drop Interval: 10 sec
Number of Sets: 53
Number of Drops: 100

Gravity Corrections
Earth Tide (ETGTAB): -14.60 μ Gal
Ocean Load: -0.03 μ Gal
Polar Motion: -2.70 μ Gal
Barometric Pressure: 3.15 μ Gal
Transfer Height: 30.45 μ Gal
Reference Xo: 0.00 μ Gal

Uncertainties
Sigma Reject: 3.00
Earth Tide Factor: 0.000
Average Earth Tide Uncertainty: 0.00 μ Gal
Ocean Load Factor: 0.00
Average Ocean Load Uncertainty: 0.00 μ Gal
Barometric: 0.00 μ Gal
Polar Motion: 0.00 μ Gal
Laser: 0.00 μ Gal
Clock: 0.00 μ Gal
System Type: 0.00 μ Gal
Tidal Swell: 0.00 μ Gal
Water Table: 0.00 μ Gal
Unmodeled: 0.00 μ Gal
System Setup: 0.00 μ Gal
Gradient: 0.000 μ Gal (0.000 μ Gal/cm)

Comments:
Files Merged:
OB20180917.fg5
OB20180917a.fg5

52	12:20:52	261	2018	980239668.234	6.915	0.695	0.695	-29.806	-0.687	2.978	-2.697	30.449	0.002	0.000	0.000	0.000	33.068811.275	-0.007	85.626	-2.222	0.000	0.000	0.000	99	1
53	12:50:50	261	2018	980239670.060	6.029	0.606	0.606	-39.429	-0.560	2.910	-2.697	30.449	0.002	0.000	0.000	0.000	33.046811.050	-0.007	88.424	-2.889	0.000	0.000	0.000	99	1

Figure 2. Plot of the set gravity values (1 set = 100 drops).

Figure 3. Plot of the set sensor parameters (1 set = 100 drops).

Figure 4. Plot of the set corrections values (1 set = 100 drops).